

Omics Techniques: Revolutionizing Biomedical Research and Applications

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Abstract: *Omics techniques have revolutionized the field of biomedical research, enabling comprehensive and high-throughput analysis of various biological components, such as genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and epigenomics. These powerful methodologies have greatly contributed to our understanding of biological systems and their role in health and disease. This review article explores the applications of omics techniques in diverse areas of research, including disease diagnostics, biomarker discovery, drug development, and personalized medicine. It also highlights the challenges and future prospects of omics technologies, emphasizing their potential impact on advancing healthcare and precision medicine.*

Keywords: *omics techniques, genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and epigenomics*

1. Introduction

The advent of high-throughput technologies and the development of omics techniques have transformed the field of biomedical research. Omics methodologies provide a holistic view of biological systems, allowing researchers to explore the interactions and dynamics of various molecular components.

The classical genomic studies include very burdensome methods to handle the complex and large genomes, whereas with the advent of high-throughput sequencing technologies, a period known as the “Genomics Era” has been formed. However, after the revolutionary innovation of pyrosequencing, it is possible to make hundreds and thousands of 16S rRNA gene amplicons in a single run with multiple samples (Sogin et al., 2006).

Hence, the rapid development of next-generation sequencing (NGS) and mass spectrometry (MS), made it easier and faster to understand the functions of biomolecules through bioinformatics pipelines. Proteomics have also become an interface between genotypic and phenotypic expressions, which gained support from diverse marine fields such as environmental toxicology, nutraceutical development, aquaculture, and disease–pathogen relationships (McDonald and Yates, 2002).

This section provides an overview of the different omics techniques, including genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and epigenomics, and their significance in unraveling complex biological processes.

2. Genomics

Discovering new taxa are appreciable but are often biased and of limited value owing to the inability to cultivate, which can be supplanted by molecular-based approaches like PCR amplification of the 16S/18S ribosomal RNA gene, cloning and Sanger sequencing for the identification of bacteria/fungi. There are several online data portals for marine genome data analysis such as “Metazome” (<https://metazome.jgi.doe.gov>), (Goodstein et al., 2012), “Compagen” (<http://compagen.org>), (Hemmrich and Bosch, 2008), and “OIST Genomic Projects” (<http://marinegenomics.oist.jp>). A new website named “Reefgenomics” was also introduced, which downloads sequences of an organism, to explore available genomic features and a BLAST interface to search through it (Liew et al., 2016).

The limitation of sequencing environmentally important organisms like diatoms was culturing these organisms in vitro and conducting studies based on functional genomics approaches which were made possible using NGS. The silicate exoskeletons of these diatoms form the functionalized silica by mimicking biochemical process for nanotechnology applications (Titilade and Olalekan, 2015).

The transposon-based integration system is one of the powerful tools used for transgenesis in the marine annelid *Platynereis dumerilii*, an experimental model for evolutionary developmental biological studies, especially for eye and brain development (Backfisch et al., 2013, 2014). Cell ablation helps in studying the functional requirement of individual or groups of cells. Two methods have mainly been developed in *Platynereis*: laser assisted and chemically mediated induction of apoptosis. The latter is based on the transgenic expression of bacterial enzyme nitroreductase (Ntr). This Ntr coding sequence is linked to a fluorescent reporter gene, thereby monitoring the specific cells in vivo. Metronidazole (mtz), a nitroimidazole compound will be converted into a highly toxic DNA cross-linking agent by Ntr enzyme, which subsequently induces apoptosis (Curado et al., 2008).

Genome editing technologies have come a long way in identifying gene-specific functions. “Transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALENs)”, a genome editing technology, consists of 34 amino acid repeats and has two domains, of which one will bind to DNA whereas the other acts as a nonspecific DNA cleaving nuclease (Cermak et al., 2011).

Zinc finger nucleases (ZFN) can be used to create double-stranded breaks, whereby the cell itself starts its DNA repair process by homologous recombination and non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) (Jinek et al., 2012).

The other promising technology that has been recently developed is the Cas9/CRISPR system which uses small chimeric guide RNA (sgRNA) complementary to the specific target site at the 5’ end and Cas9 endonuclease domain which will bind to 3’ secondary structures. The sgRNA

thus anneals to 100% matching sequence and Cas9 gets activated and cleaves the DNA upstream of PAM sequence. TALENs can tolerate a great degree of sequence mismatch compared to the CRISPR/Cas 9 system (Wu et al., 2014). Off-target effects, the major limitation in the CRISPR/Cas 9 system have been ruled out by using two CRISPR guide RNAs that bind opposite to DNA strands combined with a modified Cas9 enzyme which functions as nickase (Ran et al., 2013).

“Morpholino oligonucleotides (MOs)”, the most widely used antisense knockdown tool in the model organism “Zebrafish”, includes splice blocking and translational blocking. In order to identify the quality and quantity of any new transcripts and to knock down wild type mRNA, RT-PCR was used. It can be utilized to screen a small set of candidate genes followed by a directed knockout of the best candidate, which is inexpensive and easy, but is impractical with ZFN technology, as it still uses traditional genetic approaches for the screening (Zantke et al., 2014).

In marine model species such as fish, amphibians etc., “morpholinos” have made a significant role in understanding gene function, and have been proven to be viable and useful tools for analyzing gene functions during embryonic and larval development (Conzelmann et al., 2013) The study of an organism's complete set of DNA sequences has been instrumental in elucidating the genetic basis of diseases, identifying genetic variations, and understanding evolutionary relationships. This section discusses the applications of genomics in precision medicine, pharmacogenomics, and population genetics. It also covers the advancements in sequencing technologies, such as next-generation sequencing (NGS) that have significantly enhanced our ability to analyze genomes at unprecedented scales.

Genomics is the study of an organism's entire genome, the complete set of DNA instructions that defines its inherited traits. The field has experienced rapid advancements in recent years, particularly in the areas of precision medicine, pharmacogenomics, and population genetics. This progress has been fueled by the development of advanced sequencing technologies like next-generation sequencing (NGS), which enables large-scale genomic analysis.

Precision medicine is an emerging approach to healthcare that takes into account individual genetic makeup, lifestyle, and environmental factors to develop personalized treatment plans. Genomics plays a crucial role in this field by identifying genetic variations that contribute to an individual's susceptibility to diseases and their response to treatments. By understanding these variations, healthcare providers can tailor medical interventions to maximize effectiveness and minimize adverse effects.

Pharmacogenomics is another application of genomics that focuses on how an individual's genetic makeup can influence their response to drugs. This discipline aims to optimize drug therapy by predicting an individual's response to a specific medication, helping to avoid adverse drug reactions and increase treatment efficacy. Genomic data can help identify which patients are

likely to benefit from a specific drug, as well as inform the development of new drugs that target specific genetic pathways.

Population genetics is a field that studies the distribution of genetic variations within populations and how these variations change over time. By analyzing genomic data from large groups of individuals, researchers can identify patterns of genetic diversity and gain insights into the evolutionary history of populations. This knowledge can help us understand the genetic basis of complex traits and diseases, as well as inform public health initiatives and conservation efforts.

The advancements in sequencing technologies, particularly NGS, have significantly enhanced our ability to analyze genomes at an unprecedented scale. NGS allows researchers to simultaneously sequence millions of DNA fragments, generating large amounts of data quickly and cost-effectively. This has revolutionized genomics research, enabling more detailed and comprehensive studies of genetic variation across individuals and populations.

Genomics has far-reaching applications in precision medicine, pharmacogenomics, and population genetics, driven by advancements in sequencing technologies like NGS. These developments provide valuable insights into the genetic basis of disease, inform personalized healthcare strategies, and deepen our understanding of human populations' genetic diversity.

3. Transcriptomics

Transcriptomics focuses on the study of RNA molecules, including messenger RNA (mRNA) and non-coding RNAs, to gain insights into gene expression patterns and regulatory mechanisms. This section explores how transcriptomics has revolutionized our understanding of cellular processes, gene regulation, and disease mechanisms. It also discusses the application of transcriptomics in biomarker discovery, drug target identification, and cancer research.

Transcriptomics is an emerging field in functional genomics which aims at quantifying the mRNA molecules. Quantitative analysis of gene expression can be done under certain experimental conditions, which function in a similar metabolic pathway, showing similar expression patterns in transcription profiling (Quackenbush, 2003).

In order to quantify, several methods such as Quantitative Real-Time Reverse Transcription-PCR (qRT-PCR) (Iizuka et al., 1994), Serial Analysis of Gene Expression (SAGE) and microarrays are used (Velculescu et al., 1995).

Quantitative real-time RT-PCR is used for detecting and quantifying low abundance mRNA which is transcribed into cDNA using reverse transcriptase. The cDNA that carries the gene of interest is amplified using gene specific primers and monitored using fluorescent dyes. Serial Analysis of Gene Expression (SAGE), a high throughput method for quantitative analysis of mRNA based on sequencing tags, includes cDNA synthesized using biotinylated oligo (dT)

primers which in turn bind to poly-A tail at the 5' end of mRNA. The double-stranded cDNA thus formed will be bound to streptavidin beads at the primer region and afterwards will be cleaved with restriction enzyme to obtain small fragments. The high amount of source poly-A RNA being a limitation, led to the development of modified MicroSAGE protocol which required only 1 ng of RNA (Datson et al., 1999). Shotgun transcriptomics approaches were widely used for obtaining high coverage of complete transcripts.

High throughput methods are applied instead of conventional Sanger sequencing methods; thereby the resulting sequence reads can be mapped and analyzed quantitatively. Microarrays have made a drastic change in genomic studies due to their capacity to analyze a large number of samples at a time. DNA molecules with defined nucleotide sequences are attached to a solid support surface, commonly glass. The cDNA is labeled with a fluorescent marker which allows the quantification of a number of DNA copies. By parallel hybridization, these labeled ones hybridize with their single stranded counterparts on the surface of microarray and are measured with a detector.

Various companies are commercially making microarrays using ink jet technology and photolithographic processes. Microarray technology has not been popularized well in marine biology, and the generation of the first dolphin-specific microarray is a great advance in this field. Because of the complexity of the other organisms, genome microarray technology is still limited in interpreting the results (Ellis et al., 2009).

RNA-Seq combines high throughput sequencing with computational methods to quantify transcripts present in RNA samples and includes breaking the transcriptome into short fragments, thereby aligning the reads to a reference genome with computational tools (Wang et al., 2009). RNA-sequencing has rapidly developed with the high throughput sequencing technologies and overtook microarrays as the dominant transcriptomic method in recent years (Su et al., 2014). Single cell transcriptomes have started emerging in the marine field where transcriptomes of individual cells are directly interrogated in fixed tissues (Lee et al., 2014).

Transcriptomic studies have helped to improve the knowledge between sources and biochemical pathways that generate compounds with regard to environmental conditions. Saxitoxin (a powerful neurotoxin) affects sodium channel function; these were thought to be initially encoded and produced by bacteria associated with dinoflagellates in the genus *Alexandrium*. However, by identifying transcriptional patterns it has been found that the nuclear genomes of these dinoflagellates also contribute a major role (Stüken et al., 2011).

Transcriptomic investigations have uncovered many factors which involve host invasion, cytotoxicity, metabolism, virulence and immunosuppression, etc., in marine protists.

The pearl sac transcriptome of *Pinctada maxima* and *Pinctada margaritifera* were sequenced to study the expression patterns of mollusk bio mineralization genes. It was found that the donor mantle tissue is primarily responsible for the expression of these genes in the pearl sac (McGinty et al., 2012).

Transcriptomes retrieve only the genes that are expressed at the time of sampling and hence cannot define all genetic features of an individual organism. This can be resolved to some extent by carrying out multiple transcriptomic analysis from a species under different environmental conditions (Liu et al., 2015). Most of the species have not been able to be cultured under *in vitro* conditions and thus are unavailable for transcriptome sequencing. A partial solution involves direct sampling from the environment; the problem still includes annotation of many genes, which have not even been assigned to a particular taxon (Alexander et al., 2015). Finally, the limitations faced in most transcriptomic studies are related to the use of RNA in these complex samples, which in turn hampers the data interpretation. Most of the environmental samples are diversified in nature and have a high level of environmental complexity which makes them difficult in whole transcriptomic analysis.

4. Proteomics

Proteomics involves the large-scale study of proteins and their functions within a biological system. It provides valuable information about protein expression levels, post-translational modifications, and protein-protein interactions. This section outlines the applications of proteomics in disease profiling, drug target validation, and personalized medicine. It also highlights the emerging techniques, such as mass spectrometry and protein microarrays, driving proteomics research.

Proteomics describes the study of a complete proteome encoded by a genome. Proteomics started by the invention of highly sensitive two-dimensional polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (2D-PAGE), and allowed the visualization of changed protein concentrations in an organism when exposed to different environmental conditions. Proteomics bridges the gap between genotypic and phenotypic variability; it has a diverse application in marine biology. It can provide functional information regarding biosynthetic pathways and how well the novel marine products are formed, and can be used for commercial purposes. Proteomic tactics have been broadly classified as bottom-up, middle-down, and top-down (Figure 1), which are used for identifying and characterizing protein-peptides (Zhou et al., 2011). Shotgun or discovery or bottom-up proteomics are initially subjected to proteolysis;

Figure 1. Work flow of proteomic analysis: top-down and bottom-up

the resulting peptide fragments are then analyzed by LC-MS/MS, with the use of high-resolution ion-trap quadrupole time-of-flight (Q-TOF), or hybrid ion trap/Orbitrap mass spectrometers (Domon and Aebersold, 2010; Han et al., 2008; Yates et al., 2009). In top-down approaches proteins are directly introduced to gas-phase fragmentation for MS analysis (Calligaris et al., 2011), by separating the intact proteins with linear trap quadrupole (Macek et al., 2006), whereas in middle-down proteomics, restricted protein cleavage protocols were used to generate long peptide fragments (Calligaris et al., 2011; Wu et al., 2005).

Two ionization techniques are mainly used in proteomics: the soft ionization methods of nano-electrospray ionization (ESI) and matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization (MALDI).

These ionization sources made the analysis of protein easy by directly subjecting tissue using atmospheric pressure ionization mass spectrometers (Inutan et al., 2011). Mass analyzers are categorized into scanning and ion-beam analyzers (quadrupole, TOF) and trapping analyzers (ion-trap, orbitrap, Fourier transform ion cyclotron [FT-ICR]).

The research on microbial proteomics was mainly focused on model organisms for which entire genome sequences are readily available (Table 1).

The proteomes of *Pseudoalteromonas* sp. have been analyzed for their bioactive compound production (Evans et al., 2007). Some deep-sea symbiont tube worms (*Riftiapachytila*) which are unculturable were examined using the aforementioned gel visualization technique (Markert et al.,

2007). In order to understand the toxicity of proteomic studies of dinoflagellates due to their harmful algal blooms (HABs), research has been done under different environmental conditions (Hallegraeff, 2005). Techniques such as 2-DE followed by MALDI-TOF-MS and LC-MS/MS were used to identify biomarkers for toxic HABs (Bertomeu and Morse, 2003).

Table 1 describes various proteomic techniques and their analyses used in different marine organisms.

Proteomic studies have been used to detect the exposure levels of environmental pollutants and diseases in coastal invertebrates such as mussels, oysters etc., (Tomanek et al., 2011; Wong et al., 2011). Proteomics has a wide application in monitoring seafood safety by identifying the toxic levels of proteins and metals present in wild population or cultured fishes. A major limitation faced by the proteomic studies is the lack of available annotated genomes and proteomes for marine organisms.

In spite of this fact, there is no doubt that marine proteomics is rapidly expanding in molecular research where the elucidation of these marine bioactive molecules will be beneficiary to our lives.

Table 1 Different proteomic methods used in marine organisms.

Methodology	Organism	Summary	Reference
QTOF Western blotting	Bryozoan, <i>Bugula neritina</i>	Proteins involved in energy metabolism and structural Molecules	Zhang et al., 2010
iTRAQ labeling metabolic labeling SEQUEST	<i>Sphingopyxis alaskensis</i>	Differential expression during growth phases in response to solar radiation, temperature	Matallana-Surget et al., 2009
HPLC-ICP-MS, nanoLC-ESI-QTRAP-MS	Harbor seal, <i>Phoca vitulina</i>	Transferrin, the iron transport protein identified	Grebe et al., 2011
2-DE, MALDI-TOF	<i>Thalassiosira pseudonana</i> (Diatom)	Effects on photosynthesis and Metabolism	Hockin et al., 2012
1-DE, HPLC-LTQ-Orbitrap XL and MALDI TOF/TOF, MS/MS	Dinoflagellate (harmful algal bloom species), <i>Karenia mikimotoi</i>	Photorespiration, reproduction, growth, protein modification, cytoskeletal stability and signal transduction	Lee et al., 2011

¹⁵ N stable isotope labeling (SILAC), HPLC-MS/MS	Green algae, <i>Ostreococcus tauri</i>	Protein degradation	Martin et al., 2011
2-DE, immunoblotting	Clam, <i>Ruditapes decussates</i>	Potential markers of oxidative stress located	Chora et al., 2010
2-D DIGE, MALDI-TOF MS/MS	Mussel, <i>Bathymodius azoricus</i>	Proteome adaptation to environmental conditions	Company et al., 2011
FTICR-MS	Scallop, <i>Chlamys farreri</i>	Molecular chaperones and proteins in the antioxidant system as important targets	Huan et al., 2011
SELDI-TOF MS	Atlantic cod, <i>Gadus morhua</i>	Estrogen-responsive protein Patterns	Nilsen et al., 2011
microarray analysis, Q-PCR	Flatfish, <i>Solea senegalensis</i>	Testis proteins profiling	Forne et al., 2011

5. Metabolomics

Metabolomics focuses on the comprehensive analysis of small molecules, known as metabolites, involved in metabolic pathways. By examining the metabolic profiles of cells, tissues, or organisms, metabolomics offers insights into disease mechanisms, biomarker discovery, and drug toxicity. This section explores the applications of metabolomics in fields such as cancer research, pharmacology, and nutritional sciences. It also discusses the integration of metabolomics data with other omics data for systems biology approaches.

The well-documented marine metabolites are around 22,000 and the metabolite profiling has been intercalated with other layers of “omics” thereby aiding in understanding different biological processes, interactions between organisms and niches. Formation of primary metabolism, secondary metabolism, genetic expression, and cellular structures guarantees their basic welfare for survival. Metabolomics is the study of metabolites that are produced within an organism and it acts as an echo of enzymatic pathways and networks encoded within the genome (Villas-Bôas et al., 2005).

Metabolomics studies are still in their infancy stage due to the lack of reference databases and the complexity of sample preparation (Motti, 2012). The advantage is that it can lead to the development of hypotheses due to the discovery of unexpected relationships and metabolite responses (Glass and Hall, 2008; Kell and Oliver, 2004). A comprehensive investigation of the same will provide a viable

solution to the impeded complexity and dynamics of sentinel species. Furthermore, laboratories undergoing metabolomics research lack the interdisciplinary collaborations to continue with further studies in analyzing metabolites with respect to the commercialization process.

The great risk associated with complete dependency on these compiled data is to address the impact related to the above issues which will provide a promising future for this exciting field of marine metabolomics.

6. Epigenomics

Epigenomics investigates heritable changes in gene expression patterns that do not involve alterations in the DNA sequence. It involves the study of DNA methylation, histone modifications, and non-coding RNAs, among others. This section discusses the role of Epigenomics in understanding development, disease susceptibility, and therapeutic interventions. It also explores the potential of epigenetic biomarkers and epigenetic therapies in precision medicine.

Epigenomics is a rapidly growing field that studies how gene expression is regulated through modifications to the DNA molecule and associated proteins that control gene expression. This field is of great interest to researchers across many fields, including genetics, molecular biology, and medicine. Overall, I believe that epigenomics has the potential to revolutionize our understanding of gene regulation and provide new insights into disease mechanisms and potential therapies.

One of the most exciting aspects of epigenomics is its potential to explain how environmental factors can influence gene expression and ultimately contribute to disease. For example, researchers have found that certain environmental factors, such as diet and exposure to toxins, can cause changes in the epigenetic marks on DNA that can lead to the development of diseases such as cancer and diabetes. By understanding how these environmental factors affect gene expression through epigenetic modifications, we may be able to develop new strategies for preventing and treating these diseases.

Another exciting area of research in epigenomics is the development of new diagnostic tools and therapies. For example, researchers are using epigenetic markers to develop new diagnostic tests for cancer and other diseases that can detect changes in gene expression before symptoms appear. Additionally, researchers are exploring the potential of using epigenetic therapies to target specific genes that are involved in disease progression. This could lead to the development of more precise and effective treatments for a wide range of diseases.

Overall, I believe that epigenomics is a fascinating and rapidly evolving field that has the potential to transform our understanding of gene regulation and disease mechanisms. While there is still much to be learned about epigenetics, the research being conducted in this field is already yielding important insights into how genes are regulated and how we can use this knowledge to improve human health.

7. Conclusion

Omics techniques have revolutionized biomedical research by providing a comprehensive understanding of complex biological systems. The applications of genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and epigenomics have significantly impacted disease diagnostics, biomarker discovery, drug development, and personalized medicine. As technology continues to advance, omics techniques are poised to play an even greater role in advancing healthcare and precision medicine, ushering in a new era of transformative discoveries.

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